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CALCULATION OF THE OPERATING LOAD OF TIRES OF MINING DUMP TRUCKS

Key words: Oversized tires (OTS), tires, chambers, rim tapes, valves, factors, wear, destruction, monitoring system, economic effect, heavy vehicle.

Annotation: The quarry is based on the development of a methodology for measuring the tire distance of dump trucks. In this study, it is possible to review and analyze quarry-operated heavy-duty vehicles, the effect of tires on the tires of heavy-duty vehicles operating under the influence of key factors, the static variable normal load impact analysis and the dynamics of the process of heavy-duty vehicle tires, the development of a method of standardizing the tires of mining dump trucks increases the durability of heavy-duty vehicle tires.

The above information will help you move on to the next step. A priori information gives some ideas about the nature of the action of factors. The sources of such information can be the theory of the process under study, experience with similar processes or preliminary experience, etc. It is also worth considering the fact that the experiment is carried out in a local area of the factor space and the coefficient reflects the influence of this factor only in this area. It is not known in advance to what extent the results can be extended to other areas. In this case, such a priori information is research in the field of technical operation of tires. To confirm or refute the correspondence of the calculated values to a priori information, it is necessary to build a dependence that has a form similar to this information. A priori information is a curve plotted in two-dimensional space, showing the nature of the relationship between tire life and internal pressure. In this case, a three-dimensional response surface was obtained, which shows the nature of the dependence of the

intensity of tire wear on two factors. To build a dependence on one factor, it is necessary to consider the curve obtained in the section of the response surface parallel to the coordinate axis of the considered factor. From an analytical point of view, it is necessary to “stop” some of the considered factors in some value, and calculate the intensity several times, with a constant enumeration of the accepted values of the factor according to the principle from the minimum to the maximum. In this case, a series of values will be obtained, representing a curve describing the dependence of the wear rate on the pressure factor. The bus resource I can be determined by the following relation

$$I = \frac{H}{J}$$

where H is the tread depth of the new tire minus the residual tread depth at which the tire is written off, $H = 150 - 25 = 125$ mm; J - average wear intensity. Let us consider two methods for determining the pressure in a "cold" tire, in which the nominal pressure is set in the operating "hot" tire. In accordance with the operating rules during maintenance, when the temperatures of the tire and the air in it become equal to the ambient temperature, for example, the temperature in the garage t_r , the tire is inflated to a certain pressure p_r . Further, during operation, the tire and the air in it heat up, the air pressure increases and reaches the nominal p_H value. It is required to determine the pressure p_r . A temperature field is established in the tire in use, the main characteristic of which is the maximum temperature t_m , which depends on various factors: the design features of the tire, the degree of tread wear, carcass damage, average operating speed and radial load, the transverse and longitudinal profiles of the road, air pressure in the tire, temperature and humidity of the atmospheric air. Operating modes are developed in such a way that the temperature t_m is close to the maximum allowable value $t_d = 105-115$ °C, but does not exceed it. A significant decrease in t_m compared to t_d , as a rule, is due to tire underloading, in which its operational capabilities are not fully used. An increase in the maximum temperature t_m to values exceeding t_d is unacceptable, since this leads to thermal

destruction of the tire. The change in tire pressure p_{III} due to temperature changes is described by the equation known from physics for thermodynamic processes occurring at a constant volume:

$$p_{III}' = p_r' [(t_{BIII} + 273) / (t_r + 273)], \quad (1)$$

where p_{III}' and p_r' are the absolute pressures in the tire at temperatures t_{BIII} and t_r , respectively;

t_{BIII} is the air temperature in the tire during operation.

As calculations and measurements show, the air temperature in the tire t_{BIII} differs from the maximum temperature in the tire t_m by no more than 15-20 °C, so we can write:

$$t_{BIII} = t_m - 20 \quad (2)$$

Let us consider the case when the operating mode of the tire is promptly corrected so that the temperature t_m during the year is approximately constant and equals t_d . It is obvious that such modes are optimal - the operational performance and tire life reach maximum values. Assuming $t_d = 110$ °C, taking into account equation (2), from equation (1) we obtain the following expression for calculating the desired pressure:

$$p_r = [(p_H - 0,1)(t_r + 273) / 363] - 0,1 \quad (3)$$

where p_r and p_H are excess relative to atmospheric pressure. Calculate the pressure p_r in the tire 33.00-51, which must be set in the garage during maintenance; temperature in the garage $t_r = 10$ °C, operation modes are quickly optimized. According to the table 1 we find that the nominal pressure in the heated tire is $p_H = 0.62$ MPa. According to formula (3) we get:

$$p_r = [(0,62 + 0,1)(10 + 273) / 363] - 0,1 = 0,443 \text{ MPa.}$$

Table 1.

Specifications

Indicators	18.00-25	21.00-33	27.00-49	33.00-51	40.00 - 57
Ply rate	32	32	48	50	60
Outer diameter, mm	1615 ± 25	1940 ± 30	2690 ± 40	3045 ± 45	3575 ± 53
Profile width, mm	498 ± 15	571 ± 18	765 ± 25	930 ± 25	1140 ± 35
Weight, kg	320	525	1345 ± 40	2096 ± 63	3500 ± 105
Tread depth by wear indicator, mm	37	35	73.5	89	95.5
Maximum allowable load, kg	8650	12000	24600	32500	50500
Maximum allowable speed, km/h	50	50	50	50	50
Hot tire pressure, kPa	710	670	570	610	610

Let us consider another extreme case, when operational optimization of operating modes is not performed; the average radial load on the tire and the front operating speed of the dump truck are approximately constant throughout the year and are such that during the hottest period the maximum temperature is equal to the allowable one. Obviously, in this case, the tires operate at reduced speeds in the cold season. To derive the calculated dependence, we will use the following rule of thumb: when the atmospheric air temperature changes by 1 °C, the maximum temperature in the tires of mining dump trucks increases by about 0.6 °C. This relationship between temperatures can be expressed as follows.

$$t_m = t_{mл} - 0,6(t_{oл} + t_o) \quad (4)$$

where $t_{mл}$, $t_{oл}$ are, respectively, the maximum temperature of the tire and atmospheric air in the hottest period of the year; t_m and t_o the same temperatures during maintenance.

Assuming $t_m = t_d = 110$ °C, from equations (1), (2) and (4) we obtain one more dependence for determining the pressure p_r :

$$p_r = \frac{(p_H + 0,1)(t_r + 273)}{363 - 0,6(t_{oл} - t_o)} - 0,1 \quad (5)$$

Calculate the pressure p in the tire 33.00-51, which must be set during maintenance; $p_H = 0.62$ MPa, temperature in the garage $t_r = 10^\circ\text{C}$, average temperature of the hottest month $t_{0.1} = 20^\circ\text{C}$, atmospheric air temperature during maintenance $t_{0.1} = -25^\circ\text{C}$, operating modes are not optimized during the year. According to formula (5) we get:

$$p_r = \frac{(0,62+0,1)(10+273)}{363-0,6(20-(-25))} - 0,1 = 0,51 \text{ MPa}$$

The considered cases of calculating the pressure in a “cold” tire clearly show the need to develop modes and rules for specific operating conditions. Indeed, when comparing the results of calculations using formulas (3) and (5), it can be seen that the calculated values differ by 14% - such an error in determining the pressure is unacceptable. In addition, the rules must take into account the position of the tire, since currently front tires have 10-15% more load than dual rear tires.

The results of calculation by the formulas are given in Table. 2, from which it can be seen that the temperature in the front tires is, on average, about 26 0C higher than in the rear tires during operation in deep quarries with predominant freight traffic uphill. At the same time, the maximum allowable temperature in the front tires $t_{\text{д}}^{\text{н}} = 110^\circ\text{C}$ is achieved at the operating speeds of dump trucks $V = 14.2$ km/h, in the rear tires the temperature $t_{\text{д}}^3$ is set at $V = 20.8$ km/h. Reducing the tread height allows you to increase the permissible speed of the dump truck. The limit values of permissible speeds $V_{\text{д}}$ of dump trucks should be checked and specified for specific operating conditions, especially in areas with a hot climate.

An analysis of the high-speed modes of operation of dump trucks shows that at most enterprises, especially in summer and in areas with a hot climate, the operating speeds of machines exceed the maximum allowable. As a result, these enterprises significantly increase the number of tires out of service due to bulges, tread delaminations and carcass delaminations. The issues discussed above that arise when determining the actual operating load are the most important and should be addressed when organizing the operation of tires and dump trucks at the modern level. Solutions

may be different, including those different from those presented here, but in any case, it is necessary to obtain correlations for specific operating conditions, certain sizes and tire models, taking into account the degree of wear and types of repairs performed. Without this, optimization of tire performance is not possible.

Thus, the necessary and sufficient conditions for the implementation of the entire resource inherent in the design of tires for mining dump trucks are compliance with the general rules of operation and flexible regulation of operational loads.

Table 2.

Maximum tire temperatures 27.00 – 49

Tire Position	Remaining tread height, mm	Tire temperature at various operating speeds of dump trucks (km/h), °C					Permissible operating speeds km/h
		10	1	14	1		
Front	70-72	94	101	109	117	125	14.2
Rear	70-72	68	76	83	91	99	20.8
Front	40-50	84	93	102	111	121	15.7
Rear	20-30	68	73	77	81	86	29.4

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